

LOCAL STYLES AND METHODS OF LEARNING UZBEKI MUSIC

Kasimjonova Marjona Alisher kizi

Student of Namangan state university

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8134261>

Annotation: This article provides detailed information about Uzbek folk music, songs, instrumental tunes, local styles and styles such as Bukhara-Samarkand music style, Fergana-Tashkent music style, Khorezm music.

Keywords: music, genre, style, work, analysis, status, culture, art, direction, musical genre, performance, musicology.

Over the past period, the Republic of Uzbekistan has adopted a number of normative and legal acts on the development of culture and arts[1]. In particular, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD - 3391 of November 17, 2017 “ On measures to further develop the art of the Uzbek national makom”, of May 30, 2019 “ On the organization of the activities of the state museum-reserves Sarmishsay”, “Shakhrisabz”, “Termez” and “Kokand” Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 443 of April 21 [2] , 2020 “On measures to further increase the efficiency of the fine and applied arts” Resolution No. PD - 4688 of May 26, 2020 “Culture Decree No. PD-6000 of May 23 [3].

Understanding of Bukhara-Samarkand music style. In the regions of Bukhara-Samarkand city and region, traditionally formed musical traditions - folk songs, chants, musical instruments, clapping and professional music epics, musicians, status art occupy a wide place.

The most important feature of this style is bilingualism, the manifestation of the tradition of performing in Uzbek and Tajik languages. The tradition of bilingualism is reflected in folk music in various forms.

A version of some folk songs sung in both Uzbek and Tadjik languages at the same time. It is possible that the verses of the song are sung in Uzbek, and the refrain is in Tajik, sometimes vice versa, some folk songs are sung in both languages. The music of Bukhara-Samarkand music style is also widely developed, and it is mainly related to the creativity of women. The sozanda is a solo singer who dances with a bell or a bell in his hand and sings the lines of the song. There are three to four women in total.[4]

They show their art at gatherings, weddings, and holidays held only in the circle of women. Their repertoire consists of Uzbek and Tadjik languages, and their repertoire consists of games. One of the genres that can be found in other oases in the style of Bukhara-Samarkand is the “Mavrigi” genre.

“Mavrigi” is a multi-part play-telling series in which three or more professional singers and one or two players (dancers) take part in its performance. Mavrigi is mainly performed by men in terms of sayings and dances. Only a circle is used as an accompaniment.

The tradition of bilingualism is reflected in the sayings of the Moors. Mavrigihan is mainly spread in Bukhara and some of its districts. In the performance, the soloist sings the stanza, the chorus takes part. Song consists of two or more parts, the first part is “Introduction” in a more restrained spirit, the rhythm in the next parts accelerates. Therefore, the methods are the main ones.

Ferghana-Tashkent style of music. There are various traditions, customs, rituals, songs, sayings and status ways of the people living in the territories of Fergana-Tashkent cities and regions. In

this style, works in the direction of art, such as folk music tunes, terma, lapar, yalla, song, songs belonging to the genres of classic works, epics, makomlik, etc., are widely developed in this style. In addition, children's folklore, women's singing and singing are also popular. Children's songs include poems such as "Boychechak", "Laylak keldi" and "The sun came out".[5]

Ferghana-Tashkent music style is also a song genre called "Big song" and these other styles are not found in music practice. Epics like "Alpomish", "Rustamkhan", "Avazkhan" are performed in epic traditions.

In the Fergana-Tashkent ensemble, you can see almost all folk instruments - dutor, tanbur, rubob, flute, sato, koshnai, trumpet, trumpet, circle, drum. for some of them, there are specially performed tunes. Trumpets, trumpets, drums, wedding ceremonies (Shodiyona, Duchava), tunes such as "Koshtor", "Chertmak", "Dutor bayoti" for dutor instruments, tanbur, sato, flute Words such as , neighbor, chang are mainly used in the performance of professional music. Dance tunes are very popular - "Tanovar", "Dilkhroj", "Andijan polka", "Big game" are especially popular.

In the Fergana Valley, women's creativity, in particular, saying lapar, yalla, yor-yor, bridal greetings, has become popular. The art of hairdressing has a special place. Yalla is a phrase in the form of a refrain, which is sung while dancing. When the soloist dances and sings the verses accompanied by the circle, the refrains are sung by many people present in the circle. In addition, there are professional musicians who are close to the art of Bukhara-Samarkand musicians and Khalfas of Khorezm, and they perform individually or in an ensemble.

An understanding of Khorezm's style of music. Khorezm music style has its own dialect, costumes, dance movements, appearance, unique charms and a variety of colors. This style also includes songs, lapar, maqam, and dances associated with various ritual spectacles.

In the folk music of Khorezm, to a certain extent, the closeness to Turkmen-Azerbaijani music can be felt. In Khorezm music style, both traditional instruments are wide and not characteristic of other styles, and the famous string instrument of the Caucasus is also widely popular.

References:

1. Mirkhakimova Feruza Kholdorjon kizi. [Activity of Mutal Burkhanov House Museum](#). CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HISTORY VOLUME: 03 ISSUE: 11 | NOV 2022 (ISSN: 2660-6836). 76-81 pp. <https://scienceweb.uz/publication/4566>
2. Topildiev Odiljon Rakhimjonovich, Mirkhakimova Feruza Kholdorjon kizi. REFORM IN THE FIELD OF CULTURE AND ART IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN. Web of scientist: International scientific research journal. ISSN: 2776-0979, Volume 3, Issue 5, May., 2022. 196-198 pp.
3. Mirkhakimova, F. K. (2021). The state museum of history and culture of Namangan region past and today. Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research, 10(8), 84-89.
4. Tolipov K, Usmonboeva M. Practical foundations of pedagogical technologies. Tashkent "Science" 2006. - P. 42.
5. Fozilov J., Sultanov R., Saidov H. Formation of teacher's spirituality. Tashkent "East" 2000. - P. 21.